

Soft robot for space exploration exposed to cosmic radiation arriving at the Sphinx-observatory at Jungfrauoch

Artur Braun ¹

¹Laboratory for High Performance Ceramics, Empa, Swiss Federal Institutes of Technology, Dübendorf, Switzerland

artur.braun@empa.ch

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Figure 1: Real size model (8 cm) of a soft robot photographed under strong illumination to highlight the internal structure of its segments. The segments were manufactured by 3D printing and then manually assembled.

1 Project description

Robots can replace human workers in remote or dangerous territories and environments. Such robots have been considered for example in space exploration missions (Johnsen 1972; Salisbury 1962) for Mars and Moon. The COgITOR project (Chiolerio et al. 2021) designs a soft robot for extreme environments which can roll, for example, over rough terrain such as on Mars or Moon. One aspect of the deployment of such robots is the stability against the harsh radiation in space. The robot shall be soft in order to accommodate mechanically the rough surface on the terrain and shall have a soft, self-healing skin. Such structural components are usually based on organic materials such as hydrocarbon based polymers or even cellulose (Chen 2024; Chen et al. 2024, 2025). Figure 1 shows a model for such a soft robot. It is assembled from segments with fivefold and sixfold geometry like a soccer ball, each of which contains a hollow compartment to receive a thermofluid for energy conversion. The segments are connected with plastic tubes which connect also the basins. The question naturally arises, whether and to what extent such materials can endure the cosmic radiation, given that even

Figure 2: Comparison of the flux of cosmic rays at 440 m and 3570 m above sea level classified as in the legend including neutrons, protons, electrons, photons, as determined from database values and the PARMA model and exercised in the EXPACS package developed by Sato (Sato 2015).

inorganic materials of satellite components such as vanadium oxide, are prone to defect generation by gamma rays and neutrons (Madiba 2017; Madiba et al. 2017, 2018, 2019).

Metal oxide nanoparticles, for example, are considered for thermal energy conversion so that the robot can source energy for its operation from the surrounding thermal bath even under dark. Those would be embedded as thermoelectrical fluids in the soft architecture of the surrounding robot shell. The organic materials for these are composites from polyurethane, PEDOT:PSS, nanocellulose, to name a few. It is possible to study short term effects on such materials at dedicated radiation centers which provide gamma rays, protons, or neutrons. But it is difficult to arrange for long term experiments at accelerator centers, and the laboratory based experiments are not necessarily fully representative of the natural operation field of the robot in a space mission. The Sphinx-observatory at Jungfrauoch is an opportunity to expose the materials, components and prototype of the soft robot to radiation rates ten times larger than at sea level, as shown in the computed radiation data in Figure 2. Certainly, the radiation mix on Moon and Mars may be different and much stronger because no atmosphere is there as absorber. It is not clear in advance to know which type of radiation has

Figure 3: Two soft robot models made from two different polymer chemistries in the hands of an Empa researcher at Sphinx platform on 5 June 2024.

which effect on the material. This needs to be sorted out later in separate experiments with specific radiation sources. In so far, exposure to a mix of particles from space as they arrive at the Sphinx-observatory is at least realistic.

Figure 3 shows two types of soft robot models from different polymer materials in the hands of an Empa researcher at the Sphinx platform. The purple color patches are different polymers which can serve as actuators or sensors. The soft robot in full developed version will contain thermofluid liquid and electronic components and sensors for data gathering, real-time computation and data transmission. In addition to high doses of neutrons, protons and gamma radiation, also UV radiation and strong temperature gradients are available at the Sphinx. Given that the soft robots are expected to be as small as shown here – see Figure 4 for comparison –, they do not occupy much space. A number of them can be brought to the Sphinx for exposure, and every time increment (time laps) one of them can be removed and subject to structural analyses. One aliquot may be stored in the hutch. Another aliquot might be stored outside on the Sphinx platform. So have some exposed to cosmic radiation and weather conditions, and some exposed to cosmic radiation only while staying inside the Sphinx hutch. Of interest is the molecular structure of the materials after exposure, because the radiation may break bonds in the material, create defects and so on. We can investigate these with various spectroscopy techniques in our home laboratories, for example vibration spectroscopy like infrared and Raman spectroscopy, and UV vis spectroscopy.

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Figure 4: The two soft robot models on the ground of the Sphinx platform to illustrate their small size.

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Address

Laboratory for High Performance Ceramics
Empa, Swiss Federal Institutes of Technology
Überlandstrasse 129
8600 Dübendorf
Switzerland

Contact

Dr. Artur Braun
Tel: +41 58 765 48 50
E-mail: artur.braun@empa.ch